

Scholarly Publications: Criteria, Types, and Recognition from the Researchers' Perspective

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Abstract

Based on a survey, this study investigates the perceptions of researchers in Austria concerning scholarly publications, exploring criteria, types, and emerging types of publication and their future recognition. The findings reveal that researchers value a diverse set of criteria, with content-related factors prioritised over formal ones. While traditional publication types remain dominant, novel forms like data publications and replication studies are gaining recognition. Researchers express a desire for broader recognition of diverse types of work, especially data publications, teaching materials, and software or code. The findings also exhibit the predominantly research-to-research focus of scholarly communication, with limited emphasis on science-to-public engagement. An analysis of career stages shows that pre-doctoral and post-doctoral researchers tend to be more open-minded than professors regarding the future recognition of some novel types of publication. There are evident differences between disciplines, highlighting the need for a nuanced, subject-specific approach to evaluation and documentation. Overall, the survey results call for greater consideration of novel publication types in research assessment and documentation. Accordingly, libraries should enhance their research support services to assist in the publication, documentation and archiving of additional types of publication.

Keywords

scholarly communication, academic publishing, research assessment, research evaluation, publication types, library services, survey

Key points

- Generally, researchers prioritise content-related criteria over formal criteria. In contrast, the journal's reputation plays a surprisingly minor role.
- Traditional publication types such as journal articles remain the most widely recognised among researchers, while novel types are gaining recognition.
- In the future, research data publications, replication studies, software/code publications and teaching materials should receive greater recognition as scholarly publications.
- Pre-docs and post-docs are more open to the recognition of novel types than professors.
- A more nuanced, discipline-specific approach to research assessment and documentation is needed.

Statement of informed consent

Access to data of participants who opted to take part in the survey was restricted to the investigating team and was removed before analysis of the results.

1. Introduction

Scholarly publishing is constantly evolving. Traditional formats such as journal articles, conference papers, and monographs are complemented by new formats such as scholarly blogs, data publications, and software and code publications. This evolution is reflected in the expanding range of publication types indexed by scholarly literature databases. The Web of Science Core Collection, for example, now contains publication types such as *data paper*, *editorial material* and *correction* as well as various review types (*book review*, *database review*, *film review*, *hardware review*, *music performance review*, *record review*, *software review*, *theatre review*) (Clarivate, 2023), while Scopus includes *conference review*, *editorial*, *erratum*, *review* and *short survey*, among others (Elsevier, 2023). ORCID provides a list of types of work that includes *encyclopaedia-entry*, *newspaper-article*, *review*, *website*, *annotation* and *data-set* (Blackburn, 2022).

These heterogeneous typologies highlight the need for clear definitions and a comprehensive framework of publication types that goes beyond traditional formats and takes into account the different forms of research output. To date, however, there is no consensus on the exact criteria that constitute a scholarly publication, nor is there a single, generally applicable catalogue of publication types.

We conducted a survey of researchers from different disciplines in Austria, asking them which criteria and types of scholarly publication they consider relevant now and for the future. Our results could contribute to a more comprehensive definition of "scholarly publications".

1.1 Relevance of the topic

The questions of which types of work are recognised as scholarly publications and what criteria they should meet have profound implications for academic institutions, funding bodies and research libraries. Key areas affected include:

- documentation of research outputs: Which types of work should be documented in Current Research Information Systems (CRIS)?
- research evaluation: Which types of work should be relevant for researchers' career development and research funding?
- publication funding: For which types of research output could an institution or a funding body be expected to pay publication costs?
- research support services: For which types of publication might researchers need assistance from their institutions?
- collection development and preservation: Which types of work are considered relevant enough to be collected and curated for long-term preservation?

In addition, the definition of what constitutes a scholarly publication also has major implications for researchers. Key aspects include:

- relevance and reliability: Which forms of output are considered relevant enough to be cited and built upon? Who decides on this question, and according to what criteria?
- career development and research funding: Which forms of publication and research output are recognised by the respective scientific community as well as by research evaluation and funding bodies and are thus taken into account in decisions on funding and promotion?

Publications (and thus the distinction between what counts as a scholarly publication and what does not) are a crucial factor in various approaches to determining academic excellence, for example, for university rankings, funding allocations, and faculty appointments.

In recent years, there have been debates and initiatives in research assessment aimed at greater recognition of different research findings as well as improved transparency, public accessibility and increased public involvement. The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), for instance, calls for a new approach to evaluating scholarly output. Their vision is that "the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research." (CoARA, 2023) In this context, CoARA mentions "scientific publications, data, software, models, methods, theories, algorithms, protocols, workflows, exhibitions, strategies, policy contributions, etc." as well as "replication studies, registered reports, [and] pre-prints" as types of research output to be considered in evaluation (CoARA, 2022, p. 4).

In this context, our survey of researchers may help to map the current landscape and terminology. Its results can be used to inform research documentation and research evaluation as well as library collection development, publication funding and research support.

1.2 Situation in Austria and background to the study

In 2015, the Open Access Network Austria (OANA) recommended that by 2025, all publicly funded scholarly publications should be published in Open Access (Bauer et al., 2015). Monitoring this objective requires a precise definition of what should and should not be counted as a scholarly publication, ideally taking into account the differences between disciplines.

The Austrian Intellectual Capital Report ("Wissensbilanz"), a performance measurement tool for Austrian universities, uses a very limited classification of scholarly publications. It includes first editions of specialist books or textbooks (including edited volumes and conference proceedings), scholarly journals and anthologies, original articles in scholarly journals and anthologies (including articles in conference proceedings), artistic audio, visual and data media and contributions to these, art catalogues and other artistic printed works and contributions to these. All other forms of publication, regardless of the medium, are collected under "other scholarly/artistic publications" (Bundesministerium für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung, 2023, pp. 107-109). Given the proliferation of new publication formats, it seems useful to examine what researchers define as a scholarly publication in order to identify emerging categories that deserve separate reporting in the future.

The considerations outlined above were the initial motivation for the survey we conducted in the spring and summer of 2023. The results indicate which types of publication are recognised across disciplines and career stages, which criteria are considered relevant for classifying a publication as scholarly, and which publication formats researchers would like to see given more recognition in the future.

1.3 Definitions of "Scholarly Publications"

Definitions of the term "scholarly publication" found in literature on the subject often refer to established publication formats and emphasise quality assurance through peer review, consideration and correct citation of relevant scholarly literature, and the dissemination of new research results as determining factors.

A study by Chase in 1970 compared the perceptions of natural and social scientists, using a list of ten criteria initially drawn up on the basis of a literature review: originality, logical rigour, compatibility with generally accepted disciplinary ethics, clarity and conciseness of writing, theoretical significance, mathematical precision, relevance to current research in the discipline, replicability of research techniques, coverage of significant existing literature, and applicability to 'practical' or applied problems in the field. The study was conducted among 105 natural scientists and 86 social scientists, all resident professors, who were asked to rate each criterion as "essential", "very important but not essential", "somewhat important", or "not very or not at all important" in their discipline. While both groups prioritised logical rigour and reproducibility, different patterns emerged. Natural scientists emphasised quantitative measures such as mathematical precision and empirical verification. In contrast, social scientists valued theoretical grounding, applied relevance and interpretive depth. These findings highlight the need for discipline-specific considerations when conceptualising research output.

A study conducted by Halliday in 2001 among a group of eight library and publisher representatives, including members of the Scholarly Communications Group (SCG) (part of the UK's Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC)), explored the definition of "scholarly publication" using a framework of 22 criteria to be ranked as "essential", "highly desirable" or "preferable". Essential criteria included that "the author must intend that the publication be made publicly available in a durable form over the long term", "the publication must be publicly available", "the publication must be durably recorded on some medium", "the publication must be reliably accessible and retrievable over time", and "there should be a commitment not to withdraw the publication". Highly desirable characteristics were that "the publication should not be changed", "the publication should have stable identifiers", "different versions should be clearly identified", "trustworthiness should be based on 'institutionalised' measures such as peer review rather than on personal knowledge", and "the potential audience must be made aware that the publication exists". Author identification and basic metadata were considered preferable. Halliday's study clearly focused on formal rather than content-related criteria to determine what constitutes a scholarly publication.

According to Dougherty (2018), scholarly publications should meet six requirements. They should "putatively advance or summarise knowledge", "appear under identifiable authorship", "be issued through an academic publisher", "be catalogued in university libraries", "be catalogued in curated research databases" and "belong to at least one recognised academic discipline" (Dougherty, 2018, p. 20). Accordingly, types of scholarly publication that fulfil these six requirements include monographs and edited collections, journal articles, annotated translations of classic works, published annotated bibliographies, book reviews and regularly updated electronic encyclopaedia entries, as long as they are published by academic publishers or university presses. The author points out that other publication types don't meet all six requirements but can still be considered scholarly publications, such as preprints published on a preprint server (which don't meet the "published by an academic publisher or university press" requirement) or scholarly websites (Dougherty, 2028, pp. 19, 39-40).

Simon (2021) writes that scholarly publications are comprehensive and detailed records of scientific discoveries that affect both the research community and society in general. Dhillon et al.

(2015) found that scholarly publications contribute to creating new knowledge, play a crucial role in advancing academic fields, and stimulate modernisation and innovation within academic communities by disseminating cutting-edge research results. According to Sucato and Holland-Hall (2018), scholarly publications should undergo rigorous peer review to ensure quality, completeness, honesty, and clarity. Pienta (2018) argues that a thorough literature review with appropriate citations is essential for scholarly works.

Schirmbacher and Müller (2009) refer to somewhat different criteria. According to them, the requirements for scholarly publications include accessibility, sustainability and long-term availability, and transparency in the publication process and the manuscript versions. In addition, publications should be clearly identifiable and content and authorship should be authentic and credible. There should be quality assurance and evaluation of a publication's scholarly significance and impact through indicators such as sales figures and citations, as well as formal completeness (metadata).

It is striking that while certain characteristics or criteria have been defined as essential for scholarly publications, empirical investigations into the relative importance of these criteria within the research community and across disciplines are scarce.

2. Methods

2.1 Survey

Our online survey was set up in LimeSurvey (Version 3). It consisted of six blocks of questions and was based on the results of a pre-study. The pre-study was conducted from April to May 2023 among researchers from the four universities in Graz and was answered in full by 187 researchers. (For full details of the pre-study, see the supplementary materials) The blocks of the survey represented the following categories: criteria, authors, target groups, types, deciding factors, and future types of scholarly publications.¹

This article focuses on the results concerning criteria, types and future types of scholarly publications. The other aspects are discussed only briefly.

2.2 Sample and statistical power

The survey was distributed to academic staff at all Austrian universities with the support of university libraries and administrative departments between June and August 2023. A total of 1125 people clicked on the link to the survey. After excluding incomplete cases, the final sample was $n=616$.

We collected detailed information on the scientific disciplines. For our analysis, we pooled participants according to the main academic fields in Austria (Statistik Austria, 2012). Those were the natural sciences ($n=213$; 35%), technical sciences ($n=97$; 16%), human medicine and health sciences ($n=76$; 12%), agricultural sciences and veterinary medicine ($n=14$; 2%), social sciences

¹ All options for each of the blocks can be found here: <https://osf.io/tu4qy>

(n=119; 19%), and humanities (n=97; 16%). Due to the very small number of participants from the agricultural field, we excluded this group from the confirmatory analyses to avoid an overly biased interpretation. Notably, as we could not use the same channels to communicate the survey at all universities, the participants were distributed unevenly across the disciplines. Participants from the natural sciences and humanities are overrepresented in our survey sample, whereas the technical sciences and medicine are underrepresented (see supplementary materials). This may have had an impact on the results of the analyses across all participants.

The largest group of participants were aged between 30 and 39 years (27%), followed by those aged 40 to 49 years (22%) and 50 to 59 years (21%). There were 133 (22%) doctoral students, 209 (34%) post-docs and 246 (40%) assistant, associate or full professors. 28 participants (4%) identified their career status as “other”, these were excluded from the corresponding analyses. We did not collect data on the gender of participants.

After data collection, we performed a power sensitivity analysis to see which effects we could reliably find and interpret in our confirmatory analysis. With the statistical power of 90% and a 5% type I error probability, we were able to detect a standardised effect (measured in Cohen's d metric) of 0.26 between participants in the survey.

2.3 Analysis strategy and hypotheses

We analysed the scores descriptively for all the options in a similar way. As “criteria” and “types” were measured on five-point rating scales, we calculated the mean rating across participants and evaluated its location on the scale. (See the supplementary materials for additional descriptive and inferential information) For current “types” of scholarly publication, we excluded data from participants who indicated that certain types do not occur in their fields as this would distort the analysis of variance (ANOVA), which relies on the mean values. As “future types” did not contain a rating scale, we counted the approval ratings across all participants (i.e., whether participants indicated that a type of scholarly publication should become more recognised in the future) and analysed them through χ^2 analyses. In this way, we sorted all the options according to the participants' ratings. We also split the options according to the participants' disciplines to get a more nuanced picture of these ratings. However, we only carried out analyses by discipline or career status if statistical tests for group differences yielded p -values smaller than .001 to reduce the risk of reporting false-positive findings.

In line with our preregistration,² we hypothesised that (H1) researchers from the natural sciences (compared to other fields) and (H2) academically younger researchers would be more open to new publication formats being considered scholarly publications. These new publication formats were defined as follows: preprints, research data/data sets/data publications, databases/repositories, software/code publications, replication studies, peer review reports, teaching materials/tutorials/ Open Educational Resources (OER), and scholarly blog/vlog posts. We tested these hypotheses using an ANOVA and logistic regression for group comparisons. For results, see section 3.5 Confirmatory hypothesis tests.

² Preregistration: <https://osf.io/2tpcz>

3. Results

This paper focuses on key findings related to criteria for scholarly publications, types of publication, and better recognition for certain publication types in the future (sections 3.1-3.3). Questions concerning authorship, target groups and deciding factors are discussed more briefly (see section 3.4). Data analysis and visualisation were performed using Jamovi (Version 2.5) and Excel (2021). Complete results are available in the supplementary materials.

3.1 Criteria for classifying a work as a scholarly publication

As illustrated in Figure 1, the participants strongly agreed with the proposed criteria for classifying a work as a scholarly publication.

- 19 of the 25 criteria were rated "rather important" or "very important" (M=4.00 or higher). Notably, none of the proposed criteria were rated "not at all important" or "rather not important".
- Eight criteria received a rating of more than M=4.50 (4 = "quite important", 5 = "very important"); eleven other criteria were rated above M=4.00.
- Content-related criteria generally took precedence over formal aspects such as *publication date stated*, *persistent identifier*, and *careful linguistic and formal presentation*.
- Discipline-specific differences occurred for only a few criteria, such as *based on scientific data*, *results are replicable* and *quality assurance through peer review*.

Figure 1. Most important criteria for classifying a work as a scholarly publication (all participants; 1 = “not important”, 5 = “very important”; n=609-616).

Highest ratings

- Of all criteria, *transparent and comprehensible methodology* received the highest mean score (M=4.85) and was thus rated most important by our survey participants. Interestingly, this criterion has not been emphasised particularly in the relevant literature.
- The criteria *adherence to standards of good scientific practice*, *identifiable authors*, *comprehensible argumentation*, *permanent availability of the publication*, and *objectivity* were also rated well above M=4.50.
- In addition, *citation of sources*, *scientific terminology and precise use of language*, *results based on scientific data* and *answering research questions* were also rated highly, with average scores around M=4.50.

Lowest ratings

- Unlike what some previous studies on the topic found, most of the formal criteria, such as *publication date stated*, *persistent identifier*, and *careful linguistic and formal presentation* were generally considered less important by the respondents.
- Considering the weight given to metrics such as the Journal Impact Factor and publisher prestige, it is surprising that *a publication in a reputable journal/by a reputable publisher* received a relatively low rating (M=3.76).
- The criteria *review by editors*, *review by publishing editors* (M=3.04), and *aimed at readers with prior knowledge of the subject* (M=2.98) were identified as the least important.

Additional insights

- It is possible that social desirability bias influenced responses to certain criteria, such as *adherence to the standards of good scientific practice*. Researchers may have been inclined to give answers that align with social norms and expectations.
- Interestingly, respondents indicated that it is not a top priority that scholarly publications *contribute to the current state of research* (ranked 13th out of 25 criteria), though other studies have mentioned novelty of the results as one of the most important criteria.
- Similarly, *peer review* does not rank particularly high among the proposed criteria (15th out of 25), although it has often been referred to as a defining feature of scholarly literature.

Figure 2. Selected criteria for classifying a work as a scholarly publication (by discipline, main disciplines only; 1 = “not important”, 5 = “very important”).

Results by main discipline

Figure 2 illustrates the differences between the main disciplines in the evaluation of specific criteria.

- In the natural sciences, technical sciences and medicine, ratings for *based on scientific data, replicable results, and peer review* are above average. Ratings for *editorial review* are below average.
- In medicine, there is a particular emphasis on quality assurance through review processes.
- The social sciences and humanities show higher acceptance of *editorial review*, while there is a lower emphasis on *peer review*, especially in the humanities.

Results by career stage

Ratings across the various career stages showed significant differences for some criteria.

- Professors rated *scientific use of language, sufficiently specific research question, published in a reputable journal, aimed at readers with prior knowledge, identifiable authors and citation of sources* significantly higher than post-docs and pre-docs.
- Conversely, they viewed *review by the publisher* as significantly less important than the average respondent.

3.2 Types of work that are considered scholarly publications

Participants were provided with a selection of 53 types of work. (Figure 3) We excluded those participants who answered “does not occur in my field” from our analysis as these answers would have distorted the mean value.

- The results show clear differences regarding which types of work are considered scholarly publications in the various disciplines.
- Eight types of work scored more than $M=4.00$ on our scale. They largely correspond to the types of work typically used as core elements of publication databases and research information systems.
- “Novel” or innovative publication types received moderate recognition ($M<3.50$).
- Types of work for communicating science to the public (science communication) receive little recognition as scholarly publications from researchers.

Figure 3. Extent to which various types of work are considered scholarly publications (all participants; 1 = “no”, 5 = “yes”; 6 = “does not occur in my field”).

Highest ratings

- As expected, the most widely recognised scholarly publication type is the article in a scholarly journal (M=4.95). Special issues of scholarly journals, dissertations, contributions to scholarly edited volumes, and review articles/literature reviews follow.
- Interestingly, dissertations were rated higher than habilitations (postdoctoral theses).
- Scholarly monographs and edited volumes, particularly well-established types of scholarly publication, are also widely recognised by our survey respondents.

Lowest ratings

- Of all the suggested types of work, artistic publications are recognised as a type of scholarly publication the least (M=1.73). More than half of all participants indicated “no opinion” or “does not occur in my field” for this type.
- Contributions to/interviews in a newspaper, contributions to an internet encyclopaedia, and scholarly blog/vlog posts also receive limited recognition.
- Other publication types widely used for communicating science to the public (science communication) – such as contributions to/interviews in a newspaper, contributions to an internet encyclopaedia, scholarly blog/vlog posts, scholarly websites, articles in a non-scholarly journal/medium, scholarly podcasts, scholarly videos – are not widely recognised as scholarly publications among researchers.

Additional insights

- Some “novel” or innovative publication types also mentioned in the CoARA Agreement (CoARA, 2022), replication studies, research data/data sets/data publications, preprints, software/code publications, and databases/repositories, rank in the top half of all proposed types of work but receive only moderate recognition (M<3.50).
- Discipline-specific publication types (legal commentaries, expert opinions for authorities, courts, etc.) generally received lower ratings, although “does not occur” had been excluded for this analysis.
- Less formal publication types (reports on conferences/symposia, departmental publications, articles in a non-scholarly journal/medium), which typically lack formal peer review, were not widely accepted as scholarly publications.

Figure 4. Recognition of selected (best established and “novel”) publication types (by discipline, main disciplines only; 1 = “no”, 5 = “yes”; 6 = “does not occur in my field”).

Results by main discipline

The following differences between the main disciplines reflect different publication cultures (Figure 4):

- In the natural sciences and medicine, comparatively few types of work are accepted as scholarly publications. Researchers from these disciplines gave particularly low ratings for encyclopaedia entries, book reviews, and scholarly editions across both fields.
- In medicine, conference abstracts and meta-analyses received high ratings, while there is little recognition for types of work like scholarly monographs, contributions to a festschrift or encyclopaedia/lexicon entries.
- The technical sciences show greater acceptance of conference posters, slides, master's theses, and dissertations and less recognition for replication studies, festschrift contributions, and book reviews.
- In the social sciences and humanities, a wider range of types are recognised as scholarly publications, including legal commentaries, interpretations, book reviews, and festschrift contributions. There is less recognition for conference posters and conference abstracts.
- The social sciences assigned high, above-average ratings to handbooks, policy papers, replication studies, meta-analyses, working papers, and especially legal commentaries. Conference proceedings and slides are less well recognised.
- The humanities recognise more types of scholarly publication than all other disciplines, including a range of potential science to public formats such as scholarly blog/vlog posts and articles in non-scholarly journals/media. Catalogues, book reviews, encyclopaedia entries, scholarly editions, and scholarly monographs are also more widely recognised than in other disciplines.
- The ratings for articles in scholarly journals and special issues of scholarly journals are very high across all disciplines, displaying only minimal differences.

"Novel" publication types, some of which can also be attributed to Open Science practices, show the following differences between disciplines in terms of recognition:

- Replication studies receive most recognition in the social sciences and medicine and much less in the technical sciences.
- Interestingly, research data/data publications are better recognised as publication types in the humanities than in the other main disciplines and rank lowest in the social sciences. However, these differences are not statistically significant.
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- Software/code publications and preprints receive similar recognition across all disciplines.
- Peer review reports receive the most recognition in medicine and the least in the humanities.

Results by career stage

Differences in the ratings of various traditional (e.g., scholarly monographs) vs. novel work types (e.g., replication studies) are more pronounced for professors than for post-docs and pre-docs.

- Professors rate the recognition of well-established publication types like scholarly monographs ($M=4.50$) and special issues significantly higher than post-docs and pre-docs.
- Professors give less recognition to novel formats such as replication studies ($M=3.18$) and peer review reports ($M=2.21$) than average. The results for research data ($M=2.92$) and conference posters ($M=2.72$) are similar but not significant.

3.3 Types of scholarly publications to be more recognised in the future

The responses to the question of which types of work should be recognised as scholarly publications in the future (Figure 5) provide insight into researchers' opinions on how scholarly communication and research assessment should develop.

Analysing the responses about which types of publication should receive more recognition in the future proved to be complicated. We offered five response options, three of which referred to a potential change in recognition. Further options were "no opinion" and "does not occur in my field". The latter two were used inconsistently across the 30 proposed publication types, which meant a nuanced view of the approval rates was needed.

- Researchers are most in favour of greater recognition for research data/data publications, teaching materials/tutorials/OER, replication studies and software/code publications.
- Other types of work, including preprints and conference posters, are considered to already receive sufficient recognition.
- Science to public types of work are not and should not be recognised as scholarly publications, according to a large proportion of respondents.
- There are significant differences between disciplines regarding the future recognition of replication studies, software/code publications and several science-to-public types of work. There is a call for greater recognition of replication studies, particularly from researchers in medicine and the social and natural sciences; for software/code publications, this call comes from researchers in the natural and technical sciences.
- Pre-docs and post-docs are more in favour of increasing the recognition of additional "novel" publication types in the future than professors.

Figure 5. Types of work that should receive more recognition as scholarly publications in the future (all participants; 1 = “should be more recognised”, 2 = “is already sufficiently recognised”, 3 = “is not recognised and should not be more recognised”, 4 = “does not occur in my field”, 5 = “no opinion”; n=598-612).

Highest ratings

- Respondents were particularly in favour of increased future recognition for research data/data sets/data publications (38%) and teaching materials/tutorials/OER (38%).
- At the same time, a significant proportion of the respondents (28%) believe that teaching materials/tutorials/OER should not be more widely recognised in the future.
- There was substantial support for increased recognition of replication studies (30%) and software/code publications (29%), two types of work often mentioned in discussions on research assessment. At the same time, a considerable proportion of respondents (43% each) indicated “does not occur in my field” or “no opinion”. Notably, these types of work had the lowest rates of opposition to increased recognition in the future. This shows that support for greater recognition of these types of work is particularly strong in the disciplines where they occur.
- Opinion was similarly divided for scholarly videos, contributions to non-scholarly journals, and scholarly podcasts as for teaching materials/tutorials/OER, but here, the balance was negative, with opposition slightly outweighing support.
- For databases/repositories (29%), the distribution of responses was similar to that for research data/data sets/data publications. Relatively high proportions of respondents stated that databases/repositories are “already sufficiently recognised” or “do not occur in their field”, with only a few respondents saying that this type “is not recognised and should not be recognised more”.
- It is noteworthy that research data/data sets/data publications and replication studies, which ranked first and third of all types, are types inherently connected to quality aspects.

Lowest ratings

- Annotations (6%) and registered reports (12%) – both common in only a few disciplines – received the least support for increased future recognition, each with a very high proportion of “no opinion” (40% and 39%, respectively).
- Similarly, expert opinions (11%) and contributions to a catalogue (11%) also received little support for increased recognition. Many respondents indicated that these types of work “do not occur in their field” (21% and 31% respectively).
- Few respondents indicated that conference abstracts (13%), scholarly editions (12%) and conference slides (12%) should receive more recognition.

Additional insights

- Many respondents considered conference posters (53%), conference abstracts (47%), conference slides (34%), and preprints (33%) to be “already sufficiently recognised”.
- Articles in internet encyclopaedias (51%), scholarly websites (48%), articles/interviews in newspapers (46%), and scholarly blog/vlog posts (44%), types often used for science-to-public communication, were often classed as “not recognised and should not be more recognised”.
- Contributions to catalogues (31%) and software/code publications (22%) had the highest share of respondents stating that they “do not occur in my field”.
- Annotations (40%), registered reports (39%), scholarly editions (33%), policy papers (26%), replication studies (25%), databases/repositories (24%), and peer review reports (23%) had particularly high shares of respondents stating “no opinion”.

Do you think that the following types of publications should become more recognised as scholarly publications in your field?

Figure 6. Types of work that should receive more recognition as scholarly publications in the future (selected types, by discipline, main disciplines only; 1 = “should be more recognised”, 2 = “is already sufficiently recognised”, 3 = “is not recognised and should not be recognised”, 4 = “does not occur in my field”, 5 = “no opinion”).

Results by main discipline

For this analysis we selected a subset of publication types that come up regularly in discussions about research assessment. (Figure 6) For the sake of clarity, the analysis mainly focuses on the response option “should be more recognised”. The following significant differences between the main disciplines stand out:

- For software/code publications, there is a lot of support for increased future recognition in the natural sciences (39%) and technical sciences (35%). Many respondents from the social sciences (29%) and humanities (41%) indicated that software/code publications do not occur in their field.
- Replication studies received strong support for more future recognition in natural sciences (36%), medicine (42%), and social sciences (37%). Little support and high "no opinion" rates in the technical sciences (16%, 39%) and the humanities (10%, 35%).
- For science-to-public formats, the humanities and social sciences support greater future recognition of scholarly websites, scholarly blog/vlog posts, scholarly podcasts, and scholarly videos more than the other disciplines.
- No significant differences between disciplines were found for, amongst others, research data/data sets/data publications, preprints, teaching materials/tutorials/OER, graphical presentations/data visualisations, and databases/repositories.

Contrary to our initial hypothesis that researchers in the natural sciences would be more open to recognising novel publication types, we did not find significant differences between disciplines for research data/data sets/data publications, teaching materials/tutorials/OER, preprints, or graphical presentations/data visualisations.

Do you think that the following types of publications should become more recognised as scholarly publications in your field?

Figure 7. Types of work that should receive more recognition as scholarly publications in the future (selected types, by career stage, excluding “other”; 1 = “should be more recognised”, 2 = “is already sufficiently recognised”, 3 = “is not recognised and should not be more recognised”, 4 = “does not occur in my field”, 5 = “no opinion”).

Results by career stage

As before, we selected publication types that are frequently discussed in research assessment and focused our analysis on the response option “should be more recognised”. (Figure 7)

- Professors are more reluctant than post-docs and pre-docs to give more recognition to a number of "novel" or innovative types of work and to science-to-public publication types (Figure 7). This was the case for teaching materials/tutorials/OER, replication studies, graphical presentations/data visualisations, and scholarly websites and videos.
- For research data/data sets/data publications and software/code publications, the results also suggest stronger support for more recognition from pre-docs and post-docs compared to professors but are not statistically significant.
- Post-docs and pre-docs were generally more likely than professors to express "no opinion" on publication types, while professors were more likely to indicate that certain types of work, such as graphical presentations/data visualisations, “should not be more recognised” in the future.
- For many types of work, differences in opinion across career stages were not statistically significant, including for preprints, databases/repositories, scholarly blog/vlog post, scholarly podcasts, contributions to non-scholarly journals, registered reports, peer review reports, policy papers, conference posters, slides, and abstracts.

3.4 Summary of further aspects of scholarly publications

In our survey, we also asked participants about the authors and target groups of scholarly publications, and who decides which works are recognised as scholarly publications.

3.4.1 Authors

Two questions in our survey investigated the professional background of the authors of scholarly publications. We asked about the importance of the author’s professional status and reputation for the recognition of a scholarly publication.

- Contrary to expectations, the participants indicated that the professional position and reputation of the author are not very relevant in classifying a work as a scholarly publication (M=2.57), despite the fact that an author's reputation matters greatly in academic practice. (Ray et al., 2022, p. 159)
- There were no significant differences between the disciplines or career stages for this question.

Figure 8. Role of the author’s professional background in the recognition of scholarly publications (all participants; 1 = “no”, 5 = “yes”; n=613-615).

Additionally, we investigated whether publications by authors with different professional backgrounds were considered to be scholarly publications. (Figure 8)

- Works by authors who are members of academic institutions are more likely to be considered scholarly publications. Notably, the rating (M=4.32) is well below the maximum value.
- Publications by staff of corporate research departments and freelance academics are also often considered scholarly publications, while works by practitioners (e.g., lawyers, doctors) are less likely to be seen as such.
- Publications by non-academics (e.g., autodidacts) are least likely to be considered scholarly publications.

Results by main discipline

- In the natural sciences, technical sciences, and medicine, publications by staff of corporate research departments were more likely to be considered scholarly publications than in the humanities and social sciences.
- Publications by practitioners were considered to be scholarly by participants from the medical field more often than those from other disciplines.
- No significant differences were found between disciplines for the other author groups.

There were no significant differences between the responses of professors, post-docs, and pre-docs.

3.4.2 Target Groups

Participants were asked to indicate the target audience for scholarly publications in their field. (Figure 9)

- They indicated that scholarly publications are primarily aimed at colleagues in their own academic field (M=4.85).
- Researchers from other academic fields come second, but by a wide margin, followed by students and practitioners.
- Scholarly publications are used for peer-to-peer communication rather than for communicating science to the public. All other target groups, including the general public, amateur researchers, industry, politics and business, have a much lower rating.

Figure 9. Target groups of scholarly publications (all participants; 1 = “no”, 5 = “yes”; n=612-615).

Figure 10. Target groups of scholarly publications (by discipline, main disciplines only; 1 = “no” to 5 = “yes”).

Results by main discipline

There were no significant differences between the main disciplines regarding peers from the same discipline or researchers from other disciplines as target groups for scholarly publications. However, there was considerable variation regarding the relevance of all other proposed target groups. (Figure 10)

- In the natural sciences, not only the general public, interest groups/NGOs, policymakers and politicians but also practitioners and professionals are rated below average as target groups for scholarly publications.
- In the technical sciences, industry and the economy/businesses have above-average relevance as target groups.

- In medicine, practitioners and professionals, such as physicians, and interest groups/NGOs received above-average ratings.
- In the humanities, students, the general public and amateur researchers were rated more important as target groups than in any other discipline. Industry and the economy/businesses are of little relevance.
- In the humanities and the social sciences, the general public and amateur researchers are more relevant as target groups than for the other disciplines.
- Social sciences researchers indicated that practitioners/professionals, policymakers/politicians, interest groups/NGOs and the economy/businesses are important target groups for their publications.

Comparing professors, post-docs and pre-docs, we found no significantly different views on any of the mentioned target groups.

3.4.3 Who decides what counts as a scholarly publication?

We asked researchers about the factors that determine whether a publication is recognised as a scholarly publication. (Figure 11)

- Recognition by the professional community emerged as the most important factor (M=4.61). This is consistent with the importance of peers from one's own discipline as a target group (see Figure 9).
- Inclusion in publication databases and institutional research information systems were ranked second and third, a considerable distance behind, although significant differences exist between the disciplines.
- Surprisingly, recognition by the Ministry of Science, which is essential as part of the performance evaluation of Austrian universities ("Wissensbilanz"; intellectual capital report), was considered the least important of all the suggested options.

Figure 11. Factors for recognition of a work as a scholarly publication (all participants; 1 = “not decisive” to 5 = “very decisive”; n=605-610).

Figure 12. Criteria for determining a scholarly publication (by discipline, main disciplines only; 1 = “not decisive” to 5 = “very decisive”).

Results by main discipline

The relative importance of the different factors varies between the main disciplines (Figure 12):

- In the natural sciences, five of the six factors suggested were rated below average, while there was strong agreement that one’s own professional community decides what counts as a scholarly publication.
- In medicine, inclusion in publication databases is more important than in any other main discipline and even more important than recognition by the professional community.
- Inclusion in publication databases is perceived as less important in the humanities than in all other disciplines.

Professors rate both recognition by the Ministry of Science and the institutional research information system as significantly less relevant than post-docs and pre-docs. For the other options, the differences between the career stages are not statistically significant.

3.5 Confirmatory hypothesis tests

Our study included a range of non-traditional and novel publication types, including preprints, research data/data sets/data publications, databases/repositories, software/code publications, replication studies, peer review reports, teaching materials/tutorials/OER, and scholarly blog/vlog posts.

We hypothesised³ that these publication types would be recognised more by natural scientists (compared to social scientists and humanities scholars) and younger scientists (i.e., pre-docs and post-docs rather than professors). To test this, we submitted the ratings of these newer publication types to two statistical models with scholarly disciplines and academic positions of the participants as independent variables.

We employed ANOVAs to assess current recognition and Chi² logistic regressions to predict future recognition, but we only did so when the individual tests showed a statistically significant result with the conservative threshold in order to avoid false positives due to multiple tests ($p < .001$). We then tested both predictors (status and field) in one model and checked whether the results pointed in the hypothesised direction.

As can be seen from Table 1 (left side), we found greater recognition of peer review reports, replication studies and scholarly blog/vlog posts as scholarly publications among younger researchers. Likewise, scholarly blog/vlog posts receive more recognition in the natural sciences than in the social sciences and the humanities. Regarding future recognition (see Table 1, right side), younger researchers also indicated that software/code publications, replication studies, scholarly blog/vlog posts and teaching materials/tutorials/OER should be recognised more as scholarly publications, partially confirming H2. However, only software/code publications were deemed acceptable as a type of scholarly publication by respondents from the natural sciences. Contrary to H1, respondents from the social sciences and humanities agreed to a greater extent than others that teaching materials/tutorials/OER and scholarly blog/vlog posts should receive more recognition in the future.

These findings support our hypothesis (H2) that younger researchers are more open to (at least some) novel publication types. However, we found less support for H1, indicating that fields and disciplines vary more than assumed regarding the acceptance of novel publication types.

Table 1. Summary of the confirmatory analysis (for detailed results, see supplementary materials)

	Types				support		Future Types				support	
	Field		Status		H1	H2	Field		Status		H1	H2
	F*	p	F**	p			χ ² *	p	χ ² **	p		
Preprint on a repository or preprint server	1.483	0.206	3.163	0.024	---	---	1.547	0.818	7.476	0.058	---	---
Research data / data set / data publication	1.654	0.159	3.817	0.01	---	---	6.993	0.136	11.341	0.01	---	---
Software / code publication	1.989	0.095	1.022	0.383	---	---	24.208	<.001	11.073	0.011	yes	yes
Database / repository	3.435	0.009	1.73	0.16	---	---	7.156	0.128	9.773	0.021	---	---
Peer review report	4.232	0.002	8.192	<.001	no	yes	13.155	0.011	4.917	0.178	---	---
Replication study	6.32	<.001	5.772	<.001	no	yes	38.401	<.001	18.894	<.001	no	yes
Scholarly blog/vlog post	15.504	<.001	3.134	0.025	yes	yes	24.018	<.001	15.208	0.002	no#	yes

³ During the preregistration, we falsely indicated that these publication types are also mentioned among the publication criteria (see Chapter 3.1.), which is not the case. Therefore, the confirmatory tests were conducted for current and future publication types only.

Teaching materials/tutorials/OER	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.66	0.226	20.279	<.001	no#	yes
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Note: * (df = 4), ** (df = 3), minimum to maximum sample size per analysis: n=393-595, # statistically significant evidence points in opposite direction than expected

4. Discussion and conclusions

Publications play a key role in scholarly communication, research assessment, and, thus, researchers' careers. Even so, existing definitions of what constitutes a scholarly publication are vague. Our survey explored the perspective of researchers on aspects such as defining criteria, types and future recognition of different types of scholarly publication.

4.1 Key results

Criteria: Our study showed that a variety of characteristics or criteria are relevant for the recognition of a scholarly publication. Generally, researchers prioritise content-related criteria over formal criteria, with transparent methods, adherence to good scientific practice, clearly identifiable authors, and comprehensible argumentation being rated as the most important. In contrast, the journal's reputation plays a surprisingly minor role, which seems to contradict current practices. Our results are, therefore, only partially consistent with the criteria described as central in the literature (see literature review): for example, transparent and comprehensible methodology was more important to respondents than indicated in the literature; on the other hand, criteria such as the contribution to the current state of research and peer review, were considered less important than previous studies found.

Types: Traditional publication types such as journal articles, scholarly monographs and conference proceedings, which are also core elements of publication databases and research information systems, remain the most widely recognised among researchers, while novel types have gained recognition. Novel publication types, such as data publications and replication studies, are more widely recognised as scholarly publications than science-to-public types, such as contributions to non-scholarly journals or newspapers. The demand to recognise these types of work as scholarly publications is limited among researchers, despite the increasing emphasis on science-to-public activities from funders and in research politics. Text-based publication types generally receive greater recognition than multimedia types such as scholarly videos or podcasts.

Future: Researchers expressed a desire for different types of work to be more widely recognised in the future. The responses varied greatly depending on the discipline; overall, the desire for research data/data sets/data publications, teaching materials/tutorials/OER, replication studies and software/code publications to be more widely recognised was most pronounced.

While there is a growing demand for novel types of work to receive more recognition as scholarly publications in the future than they currently do, this does not appear to apply to science-to-public types.

Authors, target groups, decision makers: The results regarding authors and target groups show that scholarly publications are primarily written by and for the scientific community and seldom by and for the general public and people outside the research community.

Similarly, according to researchers, the scientific community's opinion is the most important factor in recognising a work as a scholarly publication even more important than its being indexed in publication databases such as Web of Science and Scopus.

Differences between disciplines: The results above refer to the responses of all the participants. However, there are significant differences between the disciplines. These differences concern publication types and their future recognition, as well as target audiences and the factors determining whether a publication is recognised as a scholarly publication. These differences between disciplines must be considered when interpreting the overall results.

Researchers in the natural sciences and medicine recognise significantly fewer publication types as scholarly publications than those in the other disciplines. The call for future recognition of novel publication types is specific to particular fields. The most significant differences in publication cultures lie between medicine and the humanities.

These findings highlight the fact that a one-size-fits-all approach may not be appropriate. A more nuanced, subject-specific approach to research assessment and documentation is required.

Career stages: Professors are more restrictive than post-docs and pre-docs in recognising publication types. They value traditional types more. Post-docs and pre-docs, who tend to be younger researchers, are more open to the future recognition of "novel" publication types alongside traditional ones. This finding aligns with the broader discussion on alternative research assessment and the need to consider a wider range of research outputs in the future. On other topics, such as authors and target groups, there were no significant differences between responses from people at different career stages.

4.2 Recommendations

Additional types of work should be considered in research assessment and documentation

Our survey shows that, in particular, research data/data sets/data publications and teaching materials/tutorials/OER, as well as replication studies and software/code publications, are increasingly seen as relevant and, therefore, citable research outputs by many researchers, especially pre-docs and post-docs. However, these types of work are not yet fully recognised as scholarly publications or included in the scholarly record.

Given their value to researchers, these publication types should be accorded more attention in research assessment. There is a growing imperative for publication databases, research information systems and long-term archiving to accommodate these novel types of publication. Libraries should expand their research support resources and funding opportunities correspondingly. This could include services such as dedicated workshops and support covering the publication of data, software or code, as well as providing funding to cover costs, for example, for data publications.

More subject-specific research documentation, assessment and support are needed

Our findings highlight multiple differences between disciplines around the concept of "scholarly publications". However, while traditional publication types such as journal articles are regularly considered in research assessment, documentation and support, novel and discipline-specific publication types are often neglected. This works against the researchers' desire to decide as a community on the recognition of scholarly publications.

There is a clear need for a more inclusive and adaptable approach to these publication types, for example, when considering decisions on staff appointments and funding allocations. This is in line with ongoing efforts by CoARA and similar initiatives to include a wider variety of types of work in research assessment.

Similarly, publication databases, and research information and archiving systems should take the disciplines' differing publication cultures into account for recording, documenting and archiving scholarly publications.

Institutional research support, publication and career advice, and publication funding should be designed to take discipline-specific publication types into account.

Archiving infrastructures may need increased storage capacity and appropriate metadata schemas to accommodate additional data-intensive publication types.

4.3 Limitations and future directions

Our survey focused on scholarly publications as an element of research assessment and recognition. However, it turned out to be difficult to distinguish between publications and other forms of research performance and outputs. Future research could explore the definition of "scholarly publications" in relation to the larger concept of "scholarly output".

Furthermore, although we collected data at the discipline level, we would have needed more participants to draw conclusions about publications in specific disciplines. Our data suggests that a more granular analysis would help identify variations between the various disciplines and research cultures in more detail.

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Open Science practices statement

The preregistration can be found here: <https://osf.io/2tpcz>

All materials, code and anonymised data are available here: <https://osf.io/vn8qf>